

Lykousada Monastery

By

Entry tags: Religious Group, Christianity

The monastery of the Panagia Eleousa (the Merciful Virgin), otherwise known as the Lykousada monastery, was founded by the nun Hypomone (Patience) in Phanari, a village near Karditsa. A medieval fortress rests at the topmost part of this hillside village. The Lykousada monastery was burnt and destroyed by the Ottoman Turks in 1611; however, alleged spolia survives in the churches of Saint John the Baptist at Phanari (1873) and the Twelve Apostles at Pyrgos Ithōmis (1845). Hypomone's birthname does not survive in primary sources, and she is known only by her monastic name. She was the wife of sebastokrator John I Doukas of Thessaly (1268-1289) and a member of the transhumant nomadic group of Vlachs. Hypomone's father was Taronas, a Vlach chieftain who controlled lands in the Pindus mountain range and the eastern end of the Thessalian plateau. Even though the monastery does not survive, primary sources referring to it do and include: the chrysobulls of Andronikos II Palaiologos (1289), Andronikos III Palaiologos (1336), Stephan Dušan (1348), and Nikephoros II Orsini (1356-1358) as well as a sworn letter by Michael Gabrielopoulos (1342), Patriarch Theophilos Kokkinos' sigillion (1371-1376), a synodical letter by the metropolitan of Larissa Neilos (1381), and a sigillion issued by the Ecumenical Patriarch Neilos (1383). Emperor Andronikos II's chrysobull is of particular importance since it is the first document that mentions Hypomone's foundation as well as the estates that belonged to the monastery. The landholdings of Hypomone were 12 and were situated throughout the Thessalian plateau. Most of them are of strategic importance, pointing to passages leading to the Pindus. Of strategic significance was also John I Doukas' monastery, Porta Panagia in Pyli near Trikala. Porta Panagia stands at one of the western entries of the Pindus mountain that lead to Arta. Hypomone constructed her monastery a few kilometers south of John's, which marked another entry to the Pindus.

Date Range: 1200 CE - 1300 CE

Region: Phanari

Region tags: Greece

Phanari is a hillside village in the western end of the Thessalian plateau.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite